

EuroSciCon

20th Edition of International Conference on
Clinical Nephrology

September 12-13, 2019
Sydney, Australia

Theme:
Exploring the new technologies in Clinical Nephrology

Invitation

Welcome to Rome, the capital city of Arts and Science, and experience the science of toxicology illuminated as never before. EuroSciCon is proud to host the 20th Edition of International Conference on Clinical Nephrology, September 12-13, 2019, in Sydney, Australia. This year's theme is "*Exploring the new technologies in Clinical Nephrology*". Clinical Nephrology 2019 will provide an unprecedented opportunity for Nephrologists of all stripes and colors to share their research with colleagues, and discuss and debate the latest advances in the field. We invite Nephrologists, Kidney specialists, Physicians in related disciplines to come together and inform each other in an environment conducive to education and interaction. Seasoned scientists, young researchers, mid-career professionals and just starting out are all welcome.

With a broad array of keynote presentations, panel discussions, workshops, and poster sessions, the Clinical Nephrology is the perfect venue not only to dive into your particular interests but also to expand the scope of your knowledge. 21 tracks are devoted to subjects Clinical Nephrology, Kidney Transplantation, Urology, Renal Dialysis, Diabetes associated with Kidney diseases, Nephrology and Therapeutics, Diabetics and Hypertension, Diagnostic, Imaging and Radiation techniques, Stages of kidney diseases, Glomerular Diseases, Kidney Cancer, Chronic Renal Disease, End Stages Renal diseases, Nephrology Nursing, Pediatric Nephrology, Kidney Stones, Renal Nutrition, Inflammation and Metabolism, Urology/Urinary tract infections.

The Organizing Committee has done its best to set up a framework that we think will allow for a creative interplay of ideas. All we need now to convert the extensive program on paper to an active and vibrant Nephrology forum in person is your active participation.

A Transformational Learning Experience

- Curated to address the concerns of today's scientific world
- Be inspired by some of the world's most renowned figures
- Stimulate new ways of thinking and provoke action.
- Relish inspiring interaction between peers, leaving you better prepared to face technical and research oriented challenges.

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Why with us?

We at EuroSciCon strive to create transforming experiences, propelling researchers and organizations to interact and come up with actionable ideas thus enhancing the quality of research and development.

And here's why you associate with us

Our International Open Access Journals:

We embrace around 700+ Leading-edge Peer Reviewed Open Access Journals and a 21 Day Rapid Review Process with a whopping 50000+ Editorial Board Team, 35000+ Reviewers team and 1000+ Scientific Associations Collaborations.

Read by over 30 Million Patrons and 100000+ Facebook Likes comprehending the High online presence, our Open Access Journals serve the best blend of content and global exposure.

Our International Scientific Conferences:

With over 3000 Conferences happening across the globe in the streams of Medical, Pharma, Engineering, Science, Technology and Business our events are accredited with CME/CPD.

Moreover you get to meet the industry's high priests who come from all over the orb. You learn from the companies defined by their progressive ethos and dynamic strategies and also through the highly interactive sessions and panel discussions.

B2B Meetings with enriching interaction help building better businesses, people and world.

Other salient features comprehend:

Publishing of the accepted abstracts in our inordinately indexed journals

Each of which will be labelled with a Digital Object Identification Number (DOI) provided by Cross Ref Distinct abstract and Speaker page creation, which profusely aid in citing the research and researcher in the top search engines.

Career Guidance Workshops for students and early career researchers

Opportunity to publish full Manuscripts in our Open Access Journals

With over 25000+ Nephrologists and Kidney Specialists accessing the website, Clinical Nephrology 2018 is the most lucrative platform for researchers, academicians and industry professionals pursuing their work in the field and related. In addition to immense networking opportunities, global prominence of the research and the researcher is what we bestow our Speakers and Committee Members fuelling better outreach of the work and profile.

Clinical Nephrology 2019 Salient Features:

In a world of information overload, we focus on the issues most relevant to today's technical trends enabling our patrons to

- Congregate with most senior executives*
- Nurture connexions*
- Agenda format which incorporates ample Q&A time*
- Partake in our revamped exhibitor expo sessions*
- Meet and listen to the relevant clients*
- Unprecedented growth creating an unparalleled market place*

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How's EuroSciCon different?

- Exercises your creative instincts with the live knowledge experience*
- It organizes 3000+ Conferences across the globe connecting different sciences in 30+ countries*
- Over 25 Million+ Visitors and 20000+ Unique Visitors per conference*
- World's leading industries and companies attend*
- Career guidance for early career researchers and students*
- Provides insights you need to take your research to the next level*
- A huge conclave of high tech and science priests*

Who'd be attending?

20th Edition of International Conference on Clinical Nephrology plays host for the Multinational organizations, entrepreneurs across the globe, the researchers and academicians. Prominently Nephrologists, Kidney Specialists, Urologists, Nephrology faculty Nurse Practitioners, Physician Assistants, Young researchers, Aspiring students, Medical Device Companies, Residents and others who stay plunged in learning and practice of Clinical Nephrology and Kidney diseases.

About hosting organization

EuroSciCon is one among Europe's largest and most significant scientific place which serves as a crossroad for the academicians and industry experts to build networks. With over 16 years of Life Science Communication it focuses on to Spearheading the Transformation of Medical Research into Knowledge through Scientific Gatherings and Networking. Supporting the Rare Care UK organization, EuroSciCon is a corporate member of Royal Society of Biology, Institute of Biomedical Science (IBMS) and British Society for Immunology. Our approach has always been unique, and that difference has propelled our growth towards Scientific Serendipity.

Scientific Sessions:

- Clinical Nephrology
- Kidney Transplantation
- Renal Dialysis
- Nephrology and Therapeutics
- Diabetics and Hypertension
- Diagnostic, Imaging and Radiation techniques
- Stages of kidney diseases
- Glomerular Diseases
- Kidney Cancer
- Acute Renal Disease
- Chronic Renal Disease
- End Stages Renal diseases
- Nephrology Nursing
- Pediatric Nephrology
- Kidney Stones
- Renal Nutrition, Inflammation and Metabolism
- Urology/Urinary tract infections

See your work **PUBLISHED** in one of our related journals

- Journal of Kidney
- Journal of Nephrology & Therapeutics
- Transplantation Technologies & Research
- Journal of Clinical & Experimental Nephrology

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About Destination Sydney

Australia - Apart from being a great place to get a first-rate education, Australia is also a fantastic place to live. It provides a welcoming and multicultural society with a population that originates from around 200 countries. Australian people have a reputation for being amongst the friendliest in the world, and Australian cities are safe and clean, with low crime rates. The lifestyle and quality of living in Australia is among the best in the world. Several of Australia's capital cities regularly rank among the world's 'most livable' cities

Sydney has a reputation for being beautiful but shallow, but like the pretty girl in high school, she is often misunderstood and falsely labelled a show pony. Look a little closer and you'll find a city with a long and complex history, and one that's about so much more than being ridiculously good looking.

The Harbor City also abounds with sophisticated spots to eat that showcase the quality and abundance of local produce. Hole-in-the-wall bars are multiplying like rabbits due to a recent relaxation in the state's licensing laws, while golden sandy beaches yield to the lapping water of the Tasman Sea. Fun and often free festivals are on throughout the year, and celebrate Australia's rich cultural diversity.

Do take a trip out of the city. Two hours' drive north you'll find the Hunter Valley, Australia's oldest wine region, which is continuously producing new and innovative winemakers. To the west lie The Blue Mountains, home to dramatic scenery, bushwalks, caves and enticing spots to eat and shop. And down south there is the rugged beauty of the Royal National Park and long stretches of unspoiled coastline

Venue and Accommodation

Venue:

Sydney, Australia

Mail us to know more!

For Abstract Submission Guidelines | For Reserving your slot | Proposals | Posters |
Accommodations

No doubt you have lots of queries...

Why not get in touch..!

Drop us your query with details and we will call you right away

Register Now!

Want to be a Part of the Leading Clinical Nephrology Event in 2019?

Choose your Category:

Academic \$799

Business \$899

Delegate \$999

Student \$499

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Package Registrations

Special Price valid through November 30, 2018

HOW TO REGISTER

Visit: <http://clinicalnephrology.euroscicon.com/registration>

Call: 44-2033182512

Email: clinicalnephrology@medicaleuroscicon.org

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